

Multispectral Fractal Image Analysis for Soil Roughness Estimation at Various Altitudes

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Abstract

Image complexity can provide useful information about the texture or material properties of the acquired scene. In agriculture, the complexity of remotely-sensed images of soil or land cover may reveal underlying properties of soil and/or vegetation. However, the perceived complexity may vary along scales, as a function of the altitude of the sensor in a remote sensing scenario. In this paper, we investigate how the fractal complexity of multi-spectral images acquired using an unmanned aerial vehicle varies with the altitude, in a soil roughness estimation application. We adapt a definition of the multi-spectral fractal dimension to assess the fractal complexity of images with 5 spectral bands and analyze the computed fractal complexity as a function of both altitude and the number of considered spectral bands.

1 Introduction

The non-uniformity of a surface, either natural or synthetic, is important in many applications: from medical applications, where the appearance of tissue can lead to a benign or malign medical decision [1] to land cover applications in remote sensing and especially in Earth Observation [2]. In all of them, the analysis of the non-uniform surface is performed based on digital images acquired using any arbitrary imaging technologies. However, different sensors have different spatial and spectral resolutions and characteristics. The technological trends follow the hypothesis that increased spatial and spectral resolutions allow for a more precise assessment of the higher signal frequencies and consequently of the nonuniformity aspect.

The non-uniformity aspect is intimately connected to the notion of complexity. The notion of complexity is largely developed and used in various fields like in physics, mechanics, chemistry, and also in signal and image processing [3–7]. Lloyd (2001) [8] proposed a generic taxonomy of complexity very related to physics, and the ways to assess these different kinds of complexity: using various definitions of entropy, Fisher information or fractal models, etc.

In this paper, we focus on the application of image complexity for the soil surface roughness (SSR) estimation, in a remote sensing scenario for agriculture. Soil roughness is important for the estimation of soil moisture using remote sensing data rather than in situ measurements. We showed previously how the fractal analysis of digital images could lead to the estimation of SSR and compare its performance with two classical methods: the chain and the pin-board method [9]. More concretely, we use fractal analysis for the study of the complexity of grayscale, color, and multispectral images acquired by an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV). The multispectral fractal dimension estimation is briefly discussed in Section 2. The image acquisition and pre-processing are described in Section 3 while SSR and its estimation are described in Section 4. The experimental results are presented in Section 5, along with a discussion on the perception of the complexity as a function of the altitude of the UAV. Finally, conclusions are provided in Section 6. .

2 Multispectral fractal complexity

In 1983 Mandelbrot introduced fractal geometry to describe self-similar sets that are referred to as fractals [10]. A measure for characterizing the irregularity and the complexity of a fractal is called fractal dimension (FD) and it indicates how much space is filled by the analyzed signal or object. The theoretical Hausdorff fractal dimension is defined for continuous objects, thus not used in practice. Various FD estimators exist, allowing the fractal analysis of digital images exhibiting properties of self-similarity: the probability measure [11, 12], the Minkowski–Bouligand dimension, also known as the box-counting dimension [13], the δ -parallel body method also known as covering-blanket approach, morphological covers or Minkowski sausage [14].

The FD is often used in analyzing structures such as signals, images, or textures that manifest fractal properties in order to discriminate them [15, 16]. In this article we use the multispectral fractal dimension estimator from [17] adapted for the case of multispectral images with 5 spectral bands.

3 DATA ACQUISITION AND PROCESSING

For the data acquisition, we used the Trinity F90+ drone equipped with the MicaSense RedEdge-MX multispectral imaging camera. The Trinity F90+

drone is an advanced UAV with exceptional flight performance and versatility. It features a lightweight durable carbon fiber construction, brushless motors, GPS, gyroscopes, accelerometers, various sensors, etc. The drone has autonomous flight capabilities, allowing it to follow predefined trajectories, maintain a given altitude and execute complex flight patterns with minimal user intervention. It supports multiple communication options, including Wi-Fi, radio frequency, or mobile data, and can be controlled remotely via a ground control station or mobile devices, providing real-time telemetry and video playback.

The MicaSense RedEdge-MX is a state-of-the-art multispectral sensor designed to capture high-quality aerial images for agricultural and environmental monitoring applications. It is specifically developed to provide accurate and detailed multi-spectral data that can be used to analyze plant health, detect crop stress levels and assess vegetation patterns. The RedEdge-MX sensor is equipped with five discrete narrowband filters that capture images in the blue, green, red, rededge, and near-infrared spectral bands (see Table 1).

Band	Center	Bandwidth
Blue	475 nm	32 nm
Green	560 nm	27 nm
Red	668 nm	16 nm
Red edge	717 nm	12 nm
Near infrared	842 nm	57 nm

Table 1: Spectral bands of MicaSense RedEdge-MX sensor.

Images from the drone camera require preprocessing before it is used for estimating the FD. In this case, we aligned the group of images where each group has 5 images that all belong to the same scene and each of them represents the different bands. The order of the produced images is as follows: blue, green, red, near-infrared, and red-edge. In order to use the fractal analysis on the acquired images we normalized pixel intensity values between 0 255. Further, images require alignment, and the red-edge imager on the camera’s body is placed in the center, thus images from that sensor are used as a reference for alignment. MATLAB software is used for accomplishing alignment by applying the SURF feature detection algorithm [18].

We applied fractal analysis on 256×256 images that were cropped from the original images after preprocessing. Overall, we obtained 12 crops from each image and each crop doesn’t overlap the other ones. This process was applied to grayscale images that represent each individual band, images that are in RGB format, grayscale images that are converted from RGB, and finally, multispectral images with 5 bands.

4 SOIL SURFACE ROUGHNESS ESTIMATION

Soil surface presents irregularities and it is defined by the term SSR. Such phenomena can be the result of several natural and artificial factors such as tillage operations, land management, rock fragments, aggregates, and soil texture [19,20]. SSR is a broad term often referred to as soil microrelief that can be divided into individual indices that describe different characteristics of the soil. One of them and the focus of this study is random roughness (RR) which is related to soil aggregate stability. The term was first used by Burwell et al. (1963) [21] to describe the elevation variations at random points on the soil surface. In comparison, another index that is part of SSR is oriented roughness which describes roughness caused by tillage tool marks and wheel tracks [22].

Various methods have been proposed and used in the last few decades to measure random roughness. They can be classified into two main categories: contact and sensor methods. Two contact methods are widely used namely pinboard [23] and chain methods [24]. Sensor methods are stereophotogrammetry [25], terrestrial laser scanning [26], and adaptive depth detection by using Xtion Pro by Asus [27]. Thomsen et. al (2015) [28] applied all the mentioned methods to different management and compared the results. Due to the fact that the soil surface is randomly rough, fractal analysis could be used to assess the soil roughness. In [29] some methods are mentioned to be using fractal parameters for the evaluation of soil roughness complexity.

5 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The acquisition campaign was performed on an agricultural field within the R&D Institute of Transilvania University of Brasov (GPS location: 45.669340, 25.550753), by Smart Intuitive Drones SRL, Romania. In Figure 1, top row shows 3 crops from RGB images that were acquired at 60m altitude while bottom row is from 80m altitude images. Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of FD values of grayscale images that were converted from RGB images. Figure 2 that the two different altitudes leave a slight impact on the result of complexity analysis when it is applied to grayscale images. Figure 3 shows the distribution of FD values of RGB images from 60m and 80m altitudes. As expected RGB images present higher complexity compared to grayscale ones because of higher spectral resolution. One can note the images acquired at 80m exhibit larger complexity. Figure 4 shows the distribution of FD values of multispectral images from 60m and 80m altitudes. Again the multispectral images acquired at 80m altitude have a larger fractal complexity. The reason is that at higher altitudes, the size of the objects in the scene gets smaller and consequently the Fourier spectrum enriches with higher frequencies. At even higher altitudes we expect to observe smoother

images with lower complexity.

Figure 1: Cropped RGB images from 60m (top row) and 80m (bottom row) altitudes.

Table 2 summarizes the mean and standard deviation of the histograms presented in Figures 2, 3, and 4 in order to obtain more concise insight from the FD values. FD increases with the spectral resolution and altitudes and the mean (μ) of the data as a single value can be used to observe these changes. We can also observe that the grayscale mean value is almost the same for both 60m and 80m, in other words, grayscale (single band) images may not be enough to capture the soil surface complexity. The fact that images were acquired over the large field but at different locations and the mean of FD values is a single value, it could be used as a value for RR. Standard deviation (σ) is low across all altitudes and different spectral resolutions, which indicates the small dispersion, thus, consistency of the FD values.

	Grayscale		Color		Multispectral	
	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
60 m	2.83	0.06	3.48	0.16	3.82	0.23
80 m	2.81	0.056	3.62	0.16	4.07	0.17

Table 2: Mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of FD values of grayscale, color, and multispectral images from 60m and 80m altitudes.

In order to analyze the contribution of each band to the overall complex-

Figure 2: Distribution of FD values of grayscale images from 60m and 80m altitudes (converted from RGB).

ity of multispectral images, we performed the same fractal analysis independently on each spectral band. One can notice in Figure 5 that the blue and red-edge spectral bands exhibit higher complexity compared to the other 3 bands. Further, we can observe that at 60m, the fractal complexities across all bands are very similar. However, at 80m altitude, this pattern underwent a noticeable difference. First of all, the complexity of images acquired at 80m is larger as the direct consequence of the scaling property of the Fourier Spectrum. Smaller details mean higher frequencies which mean higher image complexity. The density of FDs of the near-infrared and blue bands images is higher than those of the other bands. One possible explanation for the higher FD density in the near-infrared band is attributed to the heat reflectance properties of soil due to moisture and RR. However, higher density in FDs of blue channel images is less intuitive but one hypothesis is the manifestation of Rayleigh scattering effect or haze affecting the acquisition to a certain degree.

Figure 3: Distribution of FD values of RGB images from 60m and 80m altitudes.

Figure 4: Distribution of FD values of multispectral images from 60m and 80m altitudes.

Figure 5: Distribution of FD values of grayscale images from 60m (a) and 80m (b) altitudes.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this article we focused on the image complexity as an indication of SSR, computed on aerial images acquired with an UAV system at various altitudes. Based on the presented results, one can draw two major conclusions: i) as the number of spectral bands increases, the estimated image complexity increases, for the same scene at the ground level; in addition, the panchromatic view provided by a gray-scale image does not allow for a differentiation of image complexity at 60m and 80m altitude, but the color and 5-band multi-spectral images allow for the differentiation; ii) at the two altitudes, 60m and 80m, the complexity of the soil, thus the estimated SSR, appears to be larger at the highest altitude, as opposed to a certain expectation. The explanation is that with the increase in altitude, the ground details are smaller, corresponding to higher frequencies in the Fourier spectrum of the image, thus increasing complexity. However, a certain flattening of the histogram of FD for the multi-spectral images can be observed at higher altitude.

For the future, we plan to perform the same analysis at more and larger altitudes and assess the impact on image complexity assessment to the soil roughness estimation, as well as on the spectral mixing due to the spatial integration performed by the imaging sensor. Moreover, to quantify the importance of taking into account the NIR band for the estimation of the SSR.

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